

**GENERAL CONCEPT OF INVESTMENT IN AGRICULTURE: ITS
DEFINITION AND ESSENTIAL REQUIREMENTS**

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Annotation: This article discussed general points about investment in agriculture. Moreover, basic requirements for investing in this field were given.

Key words: *ownership, small-scale, agro-industries, food insecurity, commercializable, noncommercializable, commercial agricultural, investment finance.*

Investing in agriculture is one of the most effective ways of reducing hunger and poverty, promoting agricultural productivity and enhancing environmental sustainability. However, for any investment to have a positive impact on agricultural production and productivity, it must contribute to capital formation at the farm level. In this respect, investments made by the farmers themselves are indispensable. Their investments constitute the foundation and the engine for sustainable development and the reduction of poverty and hunger. For farmers, the main sources of investment finance are their own savings and their fixed capital, which are used as collateral for credit. Capital formation is certainly higher for farming households with positive savings and clear, legally recognized ownership of their land. In areas where the levels of poverty and hunger are high and agriculture is dominated by small-scale farmers, such as in South Asia, sub-Saharan Africa and parts of Latin America, the average farmer earns less than half of what is needed to cross the poverty line. For small and marginal farmers with below average land holdings, the situation is even worse, both in terms of their ability to save and to secure their rights to the land[1].

Apart from the capacity to invest through the generation of savings and fixed assets, the factors driving investment for farm-level capital formation are the growth of the food value chain from producers to consumers, which includes agro-industries and the provision of public goods in the form of basic infrastructure, such as roads, electricity, education and technology. There is no doubt that more public resources are needed for agriculture. However, there is a need for new investment strategies that are centred on agricultural producers and focuses public resources at all levels on the provision of public goods in ways that complement investments made by farmers and support in. As food prices increase and many face greater food insecurity, there is global concern about financing agricultural growth in the developing world[2]. Accelerated agricultural growth is not only needed to meet growing global demand for food and energy, but is also seen as the main pathway out of hunger and poverty for many impoverished people and countries.

Global estimates of the amount of investment needed to achieve acceptable levels of agricultural growth in the developing world vary enormously, but all these estimates far exceed the current trends in investment in agriculture by governments and donors. There is no comprehensive data on corporate private sector and foreign direct investment (FDI) in agriculture. However, the limited and country-specific data collected through case studies and sources such as UNCTAD, demonstrates that bulk of the corporate investment goes into agro-industries and the higher end of the value chain. Private sector investments along value chains are opening up new market opportunities for some farmers, but it is also becoming apparent that many small farmers are being left behind.

There are signs of an increasing chasm opening up between small farms that are commercializable and noncommercializable subsistence farmers. This polarization could lead to a situation where policies and investments geared towards strengthening commercial agricultural production and value chains are not consistent with policies and investments geared to reducing poverty and food

insecurity. All agricultural investors, regardless of their size or the country, require the capacity to make investments and an environment that enables them to do so. For farmers, their capacity to invest is determined by their main sources of investment finance: their own savings and their fixed capital, which is used as collateral for credit. Capital formation is certainly higher for farming households with positive savings[3]. In the countries where the levels of poverty and hunger are high, the average farmer does not have any savings. In India and Bangladesh, more than 80 percent of the farming households demonstrate negative savings and take out loans just to cover their consumption.

In recent years, remittances from migrating family members have contributed to increasing investment in agriculture. However, policies to provide credit to small and marginal farmers, who do not have adequate collateral, have not had the desired success. Migration and remittances have recently become a main source of rural household income in many developing countries. They were found to be an important source of investment in agriculture for the development of family farming and particularly for making the shift from subsistence agriculture to market-oriented production. Migration is predominantly a family decision. It is the family that decides whom to send, mobilizes the cost of migration and, in return, receives remittances for the wider benefit of the family. However, it should be noted that large part of remittances are used for immediate consumption, health and education. Only a small proportion, around 10-12 percent, is invested in agriculture. There are several essential requirements for increasing savings and domestic investment in agriculture. They must work in tandem with each other and with sectoral and overall policies. Fulfilling only one of these requirements without considering the others is not likely to be effective in promoting investment.

People save to transfer and eventually transform their savings into capital. For this process to function efficiently, good governance and rule of law are required. To be effective, the legal system must be equally accessible and affordable to all. Establish secure property rights, fixed capital and financial

institutions[4]. Fixed capital formation is a driving force for economic growth, development and the reduction of poverty and hunger. The crucial factors that allow for the formation of fixed capital are clearly defined property rights that are applied fairly and equitably to all under the rule of law and the presence of working financial institutions. Secure rights to land encourage investment, and financial institutions enable fixed capital to become a source of investment. In most countries with acute food insecurity and poverty, most of smallholder farmers are not in a position to save. To promote farm level investment, land consolidation needs to be facilitated to enable farmers to attain a level of income adequate for positive savings. Land consolidation, however, needs to be supported by an exit strategy for those who cannot make a living in agriculture, which generates non-farm income opportunities and provides appropriate social protection measures.

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